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**Deploying a
standardized
assessment protocol
for tarpon**

Deploying a standardized assessment protocol for permit and tarpon

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Executive Summary

This interim report applies the Best Catch Assessment (BECAA) approach to reconstruct long-term trends in Atlantic tarpon (*Megalops atlanticus*) across South Florida, U.S.A. Using structured local knowledge from 119 anglers and guides, representing 3,007 years of fishing experience, the assessment generates a 57-year trajectory of tarpon relative abundance, size structure, and angler effort. Results indicate that tarpon encounter rates increased through the late twentieth century, peaked in the mid to late 1990s, and have declined steadily since. Present-day encounter rates have returned to levels similar to the early stages of the time series, with approximately 10 eats and 5 hookups per standardised fishing day, compared with long-term means of ~17 eats and ~13 hookups. Reported maximum fish size also declined from a peak of approximately 168 lbs in the early 1990s to around 90 lbs in recent years. Regional trends varied across South Florida, indicating that tarpon population dynamics are spatially structured rather than uniform. Some regions showed earlier or stronger declines, while others showed relative stability or weaker signals of change. Angler effort also showed a delayed behavioural response: effort targeting tarpon increased during the early stages of declining encounter rates before shifting once availability had fallen further. These findings demonstrate the value of BECAA as a practical tool for generating quantitative indicators in data-limited recreational fisheries. The work also supports the development of a South Florida Best Catch Assessment ShinyApp as a stakeholder engagement and communication platform for tarpon and bonefish, with future expansion planned for permit.

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Introduction

Atlantic tarpon (*Megalops atlanticus*) underpin one of the most iconic catch-and-release fisheries in South Florida and the wider Caribbean, delivering substantial ecological, cultural, and economic value (Adams et al., 2014). Their life history is complex and spatially extensive (Luo et al., 2020; Griffin et al., 2022). Tarpon move across a mosaic of habitats, from estuarine nurseries to coastal embayments and offshore spawning grounds, over long lifespans and delayed maturity (Crabtree et al., 1997; Ault et al., 2007). This reliance on connected, nearshore systems makes them particularly exposed to environmental change, especially declining water quality and habitat degradation (Adams et al., 2014).

Despite their prominence, there is no clear long-term picture of tarpon population trends in South Florida. Conventional stock assessments struggle in this system due to limited fishery-independent data, inconsistent reporting, and the dominance of catch-and-release fishing, which removes standard harvest-based indicators (Post et al., 2002; Ault et al., 2007). These constraints are typical of many global fisheries, where monitoring rarely captures long-term dynamics at meaningful scales (Branch et al., 2010; Branch et al., 2011; Cope et al., 2023). As a result, management often operates with partial or uncertain evidence.

There is growing recognition that Indigenous and local knowledge (ILK) can fill critical gaps in these contexts (Jones et al., 2024). Experienced fishers and fishing guides hold long-term, place-based knowledge on changes in abundance, size structure, and fishing conditions, often spanning decades (Tesfamichael et al., 2014; Sáenz-Arroyo and Revollo-Fernández, 2016; Leduc et al., 2021; Jones et al., 2025). When collected systematically, this knowledge can provide robust, quantitative insights that complement conventional datasets and extend baselines beyond the limits of formal monitoring (Bender et al., 2014; Lavides et al., 2016; Braga et al., 2022; Jones et al., 2025).

Here, we apply a Best Catch Assessment (BECAA)(Jones et al., 2026) approach to reconstruct long-term trends in tarpon abundance and size across South Florida. By standardising anglers' recollections of their most productive fishing trips, BECAA generates comparable estimates of encounter rates and size over time. This allows us to build a historical trajectory of tarpon populations in a data-limited system, while demonstrating how structured ILK can directly inform ecosystem-based fisheries management.

Methods

Using the final Best Catch Assessment (BECAA) approach adapted from the bonefish survey (Jones et al., 2026), we reconstructed a 57-year trajectory of tarpon (*Megalops atlanticus*) populations across South Florida. As with the bonefish assessment, this approach leverages fishers' recollections of their most productive fishing experiences ("best days") to generate quantitative indicators of long-term population change (Jones et al., 2026). Specifically, respondents were asked to report (1) the highest number of tarpon encounters from their best fishing day and the year in which it occurred, and (2) comparable metrics for the current year. In this context, "encounters" were defined using standard angling terminology and included *eats* (instances where fish ate the fly or lure, but wasn't hooked), and *hookups* (instances where the hook penetrates the jaw and holds firm). These stages represent a sequential interaction process, from detection to capture, and are widely recognised within sight-based fisheries such as tarpon angling. More broadly, *eats* may be a measure of relative abundance (relatively unaffected by angler skill), whereas *hookups* more closely relates to catchability (inclusive of angler skill).

From these responses, we derived two primary indicators of population status: (a) encounter rates, expressed as eats-per-unit-effort (EPUE) and hookups-per-unit-effort (HPUE), and (b) maximum fish size (e.g., weight). In sight-based fisheries such as tarpon angling, these early-stage interaction metrics reflect the frequency with which fish engage with gear and therefore provide a direct measure of fish availability to anglers. As such, EPUE and HPUE function as proxies for relative abundance, analogous to catch-per-unit-effort (CPUE), which is widely used in fisheries science as an index of population density (Hilborn, 2012; Lynch et al., 2012).

In this context, *eats* represent instances where a fish attempts to take the bait or fly, while *hookups* indicate successful hook engagement. Both occur prior to landing and are therefore less influenced by downstream processes such as fight duration, gear failure, or handling. By focusing on these early-stage interactions, EPUE and HPUE reduce biases associated with angler skill, landing success, and reporting practices that can confound conventional catch-based metrics, particularly in catch-and-release fisheries (Frezza and Clem, 2015; Santos et al., 2019). These indicators capture both encounter frequency and aggregation dynamics, providing a sensitive and behaviourally relevant signal of relative abundance in a visually mediated fishery.

This approach is consistent with broader fisheries applications where effort-standardised catch or interaction rates are used as indices of abundance, particularly in data-limited systems where fishery-independent surveys are unavailable (Hilborn, 2012; Lynch et al., 2012). It also aligns with previous ILK approaches, which demonstrate that recollections of peak fishing events provide more stable and less biased estimates of long-term change than average catch rates (Thurstan et al., 2016; Jones et al., 2026).

To account for variability in fishing effort among respondents, encounter data were standardised by reported fishing hours. Specifically, eats and hookups were converted to a per-day metric by dividing reported encounters by individual trip duration and scaling

to a standardised fishing day (e.g., 7.6 hours), following methods used in the bonefish BECAA (Jones et al., 2026). No standardisation was required for size-based metrics.

Adopting a “wisdom of crowds” framework (Jones et al., 2025), individual responses were aggregated by year and region to generate annual estimates of EPUE, HPUE, and size structure. This aggregation reduces the influence of individual variability and extreme values while preserving population-level signals. Where appropriate, data were pooled across regions to produce system-wide trends, while regional analyses were used to explore spatial variability in population dynamics.

Results

Using the structured survey developed within the BECAA framework, we compiled local ecological knowledge from 119 anglers and guides across South Florida. Respondents ranged in age from 19 to 85 years (mean = 57 ± 14) and reported between 2 and 60 years of fishing experience (mean = 25 ± 14), representing a combined 3,007 years of on-the-water experience. The sample included both professional fishing guides (n = 33) and recreational anglers (n = 86), with spatial coverage spanning Key West (n = 46), the Lower Keys (n = 56), the Upper Keys (n = 48), Everglades National Park (n = 49), and Biscayne Bay (n = 13).

Long-term variability in tarpon relative abundance

Reconstructed encounter rates (EPUE and HPUE) reveal pronounced long-term variability in tarpon relative abundance across South Florida (Figure 1a–b). When aggregated across regions, encounter rates indicate a clear peak in the mid to late 1990s, followed by a sustained decline through to 2025. In recent years, encounter rates have returned to levels similar to those observed in the early to mid-1970s, with values of approximately 10 eats and 5 hookups per day, relative to long-term means of ~ 17 eats and ~ 13 hookups. This trajectory is not linear. Instead, it reflects a period of increase from the 1970s through to approximately 2000, followed by a prolonged decline thereafter. The pattern is consistent across both EPUE and HPUE, suggesting a coherent signal of changing relative abundance rather than artefacts of a single metric.

Figure 1. Relative abundance and size of tarpon across South Florida, expressed as encounters per standardised fishing day: (a) eats-per-unit-effort (EPUE), (b) hookups-per-unit-effort (HPUE), and (c) reported maximum weight. Dashed lines represent long-term means; solid lines show locally weighted regression (LOESS) smoothing (*span* = 0.75).

Eats and hookups represent sequential but distinct stages in the tarpon fishing process. Across the time series, HPUE broadly tracked EPUE (Figure 2), supporting the interpretation that both metrics capture a shared signal of tarpon availability or relative abundance. Mean EPUE was 17.6 eats per standardised fishing day, while mean HPUE was 14.9 hookups per standardised fishing day, giving an average gap of 2.4 encounters. On average, HPUE was equivalent to 86% of EPUE, suggesting that most reported eats converted into hookups.

However, conversion was not constant through time. The ratio of HPUE to EPUE ranged from 0.48 to 1.63, indicating periods where hookups diverged from eats. This divergence could reflect variation in fish behaviour, angler effectiveness, fishing conditions, or recall differences, rather than abundance alone. Importantly, the broad agreement between EPUE and HPUE strengthens confidence that the overall decline reflects a real reduction in tarpon availability and relative abundance. The conversion ratio provides a useful secondary indicator of changing catchability.

Figure 2. Comparison of eats-per-unit-effort and hookups-per-unit-effort across South Florida. (a) Annual trends in EPUE and HPUE. (b) Hookup conversion ratio, calculated as HPUE/EPUE. Solid lines show LOESS smoothing ($span = 0.75$); dashed line in panel b indicates the long-term mean conversion ratio.

Changes in tarpon size structure over time

Reported maximum size from best fishing days shows a variable but directional trend over time (Figure 1c). Reported weight peaked around 1992, with anglers describing fish of approximately 168 lbs, followed by a decline towards the present, where reported best-day fish are now closer to 90 lbs. In recent years, reported size has remained below the long-term mean of approximately 100 lbs, suggesting a reduction in population size structure, although fish remain larger than those described in the earliest records from the early 1970s. Changes in size broadly mirror trends in encounter rates but are not perfectly synchronous, indicating that abundance and size structure may be influenced by partially distinct processes.

Regional patterns in abundance and size structure

Regional analyses reveal strong spatial heterogeneity in both tarpon abundance and size structure (Figure 3). Although the overall South Florida trajectory is characterised by a rise through the late twentieth century followed by decline, the timing and magnitude of these changes vary among regions.

Encounter rates (EPUE and HPUE) differ across regions, with some areas exhibiting earlier or more pronounced declines (e.g., eats in Key West, hookups in Upper Keys), while others show more gradual changes or periods of relative stability (e.g., eats in Upper Keys, hookups in Lower Keys), and even increases (e.g., eats in Biscayne Bay).

Similarly, size structure varies spatially. Certain regions retained larger individuals for longer periods (e.g., Upper Keys), whereas others show earlier reductions in reported maximum weight or consistently smaller fish (e.g., Everglades National Park, Biscayne Bay).

Variation among regions is evident not only in the direction of change but also in the timing of peaks and declines, indicating that tarpon population dynamics are not uniform across South Florida. These patterns suggest that regional differences in habitat condition, hydrology, connectivity, and localised fishing pressure may shape both abundance and size structure.

Figure 3. Regional trajectories in tarpon relative abundance and size structure across South Florida: (a) eats-per-unit-effort (EPUE), (b) hookups-per-unit-effort (HPUE), and (c) reported maximum weight by region. Dashed lines represent long-term means; solid lines show LOESS smoothing (method = loess; formula = $y \sim x$, span = 0.75).

Angler effort reflects delayed responses to changing availability

Reported effort allocation towards tarpon, relative to other key sportfish (bonefish and permit), reveals a clear but delayed behavioural response to changing availability (Figure 4). Effort remained broadly stable until the late 1990s, after which it increased markedly, even as both eats-per-unit-effort and hookups-per-unit-effort began to decline. Rather than tracking abundance directly, effort intensified during the early phases of decline, indicating that anglers continued to prioritise tarpon despite falling encounter rates. Only once encounter rates dropped to lower levels did effort begin to shift more noticeably.

This decoupling between effort and abundance highlights a consistent lag in behavioural response, where investment in the fishery is maintained beyond the point at which ecological conditions have begun to deteriorate.

Figure 4. Angler effort (% time targeting tarpon relative to other species) across South Florida. Solid lines show LOESS smoothing (method = loess; formula = $y \sim x$, span = 0.75).

Discussion

This assessment provides one of the first quantitative, multi-decadal reconstructions of tarpon population dynamics across South Florida derived from angler knowledge. The results that tarpon abundance increased through the late twentieth century, peaked in the mid to late 1990s, and has declined steadily since. Present day encounter rates have returned to levels observed in the early stages of the time series, consistent with conditions prior to the peak expansion of the modern South Florida sport fishery. Importantly, changes in size structure reinforce this trajectory. The decline in reported maximum weight from peak values in the early 1990s to substantially smaller present-day catches, potentially suggests a contraction in population size structure.

However, these changes are not spatially uniform. Regional analyses show clear divergence in both abundance and size trajectories, with some areas experiencing earlier or more pronounced declines, while others exhibit relative stability or weaker signals of change. This spatial heterogeneity points to the influence of region-specific drivers, including habitat condition, hydrological regimes, connectivity across life stages, and localised fishing pressure. It also highlights a key limitation of system-wide assessments, which can obscure important local dynamics.

The behavioural response of anglers provides an additional and often overlooked signal. Effort increased during the early stages of decline and only shifted once encounter rates reached lower levels. This lagged response indicates that effort does not track abundance directly and may mask early warning signs of population change. As a result, reliance on effort-based indicators alone may underestimate or delay detection of declines in recreational fisheries.

Next steps and additional activities

This work establishes a foundation for expanding BECAA across species, regions, and monitoring frameworks. A priority next step is the development and deployment of a complementary assessment for permit, building on strong interest from fishing guides to contribute data through periodic, low-burden survey approaches (e.g., text-based reporting). This will allow for cross-species comparison and a more integrated understanding of flats fisheries dynamics in South Florida.

In parallel, we have developed a draft ShinyApp as a visualisation and communication tool to return results to stakeholders (Figure 5), including recreational fishers and guides (<https://projectseagrass.shinyapps.io/SouthFloridaBECAA/>). This platform translates temporal trends into accessible outputs, with potential to support both engagement and decision-making. Discussions will be initiated with Bonefish & Tarpon Trust to assess its value as a stakeholder engagement and knowledge exchange tool, and whether it can be developed beyond its current proof-of-concept stage (e.g., allowing people to add data to it independently). We have made this available for both Tarpon and Bonefish.

Figure 5. Screenshot from the South Florida Best Catch Assessment ShinyApp

References

- Adams, A.J., Horodysky, A.Z., McBride, R.S., Guindon, K., Shenker, J., MacDonald, T.C., Harwell, H.D., Ward, R., and Carpenter, K. (2014). Global conservation status and research needs for tarpons (Megalopidae), ladyfishes (Elopidae) and bonefishes (Albulidae). *Fish and Fisheries* 15, 280-311.
- Ault, J.S., Humston, R., Larkin, M.F., Perusquia, E., Farmer, N.A., Luo, J., Zurcher, N., Smith, S.G., Barbieri, L.R., and Posada, J.M. (2007). 16 Population Dynamics and Resource Ecology of Atlantic Tarpon and Bonefish. *Biology and management of the world tarpon and bonefish fisheries*, 217.
- Bender, M.G., Machado, G.R., Silva, P.J.d.A., Floeter, S.R., Monteiro-Netto, C., Luiz, O.J., and Ferreira, C.E.L. (2014). Local Ecological Knowledge and Scientific Data Reveal Overexploitation by Multigear Artisanal Fisheries in the Southwestern Atlantic. *PLOS ONE* 9, e110332.
- Braga, H.O., Bender, M.G., Oliveira, H.M.F., Pereira, M.J., and Azeiteiro, U.M. (2022). Fishers' knowledge on historical changes and conservation of Allis shad -*Alosa alosa* (Linnaeus, 1758) in Minho River, Iberian Peninsula. *Regional Studies in Marine Science* 49, 102094.
- Branch, T.A., Jensen, O.P., Ricard, D., Ye, Y., and Hilborn, R.A.Y. (2011). Contrasting Global Trends in Marine Fishery Status Obtained from Catches and from Stock Assessments. *Conservation Biology* 25, 777-786.
- Branch, T.A., Watson, R., Fulton, E.A., Jennings, S., McGilliard, C.R., Pablico, G.T., Ricard, D., and Tracey, S.R. (2010). The trophic fingerprint of marine fisheries. *Nature* 468, 431-435.
- Cope, J.M., Dowling, N.A., Hesp, S.A., Omori, K.L., Bessell-Browne, P., Castello, L., Chick, R., Dougherty, D., Holmes, S.J., McGarvey, R., Ovando, D., Nowlis, J., and Prince, J. (2023). The stock assessment theory of relativity: deconstructing the term "data-limited" fisheries into components and guiding principles to support the science of fisheries management. *Reviews in Fish Biology and Fisheries* 33, 241-263.
- Crabtree, R.E., Cyr, E.C., Chacón Chaverri, D., McLarney, W.O., and Dean, J.M. (1997). Reproduction of tarpon, *Megalops atlanticus*, from Florida and Costa Rican waters and notes on their age and growth. *Bulletin of Marine Science* 61, 271-285.
- Frezza, P.E., and Clem, S.E. (2015). Using local fishers' knowledge to characterize historical trends in the Florida Bay bonefish population and fishery. *Environmental Biology of Fishes* 98, 2187-2202.
- Griffin, L.P., Brownscombe, J.W., Adams, A.J., Holder, P.E., Filous, A., Casselberry, G.A., Wilson, J.K., Boucek, R.E., Lowerre-Barbieri, S.K., and Acosta, A. (2022). Seasonal variation in the phenology of Atlantic tarpon in the Florida Keys. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 684, 133-155.
- Hilborn, R. (2012). The evolution of quantitative marine fisheries management 1985–2010. *Natural Resource Modeling* 25, 122-144.
- Jones, B.L.H., Costa, S., James, W.R., Adams, A.J., Boucek, R.E., Santos, R.O., and Rehage, J.S. (2026). Six decades of fishery change inferred from fishers' recollections of their best catches. *Research Square*.
- Jones, B.L.H., Santos, R.O., James, W.R., Costa, S.V., Adams, A.J., Boucek, R.E., Coals, L., Cullen-Unsworth, L.C., Shephard, S., and Rehage, J.S. (2024). New directions

- for Indigenous and local knowledge research and application in fisheries science: Lessons from a systematic review. *Fish and Fisheries* 25, 647-671.
- Jones, B.L.H., Santos, R.O., James, W.R., Shephard, S., Adams, A.J., Boucek, R.E., Coals, L., Costa, S.V., Cullen-Unsworth, L.C., and Rehage, J.S. (2025). Stakeholder diversity matters: employing the wisdom of crowds for data-poor fisheries assessments. *Scientific Reports* 15, 440.
- Lavides, M.N., Molina, E.P.V., de la Rosa, G.E., Jr., Mill, A.C., Rushton, S.P., Stead, S.M., and Polunin, N.V.C. (2016). Patterns of Coral-Reef Finfish Species Disappearances Inferred from Fishers' Knowledge in Global Epicentre of Marine Shorefish Diversity. *PLOS ONE* 11, e0155752.
- Leduc, A.O.H.C., De Carvalho, F.H.D., Hussey, N.E., Reis-Filho, J.A., Longo, G.O., and Lopes, P.F.M. (2021). Local ecological knowledge to assist conservation status assessments in data poor contexts: a case study with the threatened sharks of the Brazilian Northeast. *Biodiversity and Conservation* 30, 819-845.
- Luo, J., Ault, J.S., Ungar, B.T., Smith, S.G., Larkin, M.F., Davidson, T.N., Bryan, D.R., Farmer, N.A., Holt, S.A., and Alford, A.S. (2020). Migrations and movements of Atlantic tarpon revealed by two decades of satellite tagging. *Fish and Fisheries* 21, 290-318.
- Lynch, P.D., Shertzer, K.W., and Latour, R.J. (2012). Performance of methods used to estimate indices of abundance for highly migratory species. *Fisheries Research* 125, 27-39.
- Post, J.R., Sullivan, M., Cox, S., Lester, N.P., Walters, C.J., Parkinson, E.A., Paul, A.J., Jackson, L., and Shuter, B.J. (2002). Canada's recreational fisheries: the invisible collapse? *Fisheries* 27, 6-17.
- Sáenz-Arroyo, A., and Revollo-Fernández, D. (2016). Local ecological knowledge concurs with fishing statistics: An example from the abalone fishery in Baja California, Mexico. *Marine Policy* 71, 217-221.
- Santos, R.O., Rehage, J.S., Kroloff, E.K.N., Heinen, J.E., and Adams, A.J. (2019). Combining data sources to elucidate spatial patterns in recreational catch and effort: fisheries-dependent data and local ecological knowledge applied to the South Florida bonefish fishery. *Environmental Biology of Fishes* 102, 299-317.
- Tesfamichael, D., Pitcher, T.J., and Pauly, D. (2014). Assessing changes in fisheries using fishers' knowledge to generate long time series of catch rates: a case study from the Red Sea. *Ecology and Society* 19.
- Thurstan, R.H., Buckley, S.M., Ortiz, J.C., and Pandolfi, J.M. (2016). Setting the Record Straight: Assessing the Reliability of Retrospective Accounts of Change. *Conservation Letters* 9, 98-105.